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Psychosocial determinants of alternative protein choices: A meta-review

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Abstract

This meta-review synthesizes evidence concerning individual-level psychosocial characteristics associated with alternative protein food (APF) choices. We investigated the associations between: (i) individual-level determinants based on the COM-B model (capabilities, perceived opportunities, motivation), sociodemographic factors, and (ii) indicators of APF choices (e.g., intention to eat, buy, pay, acceptance, intake). Differences in characteristics of APF made from plants, insects, mushrooms, and other APF sources were explored. Thirteen databases were searched in this meta-review, pre-registered with PROSPERO repository (CRD42023388694). Twenty-eight reviews were included. The risk of bias was assessed using the ROBIS tool. For *plant-based APF* choices, strong support was obtained for associations with: (i) capabilities, including cooking skills, exposure to/familiarity with APF; (ii) motivations, including perceived health-related, pro-environmental, and sustainability benefits, animal welfare; (iii) sociodemographic characteristics, namely younger age and higher education. For *insect-based APF* choices, strong support was obtained for: (i) capabilities, including formal knowledge about APF, exposure to/familiarity with APF; (ii) perceived opportunities, encompassing positive social and cultural norms, distrust in technology; (iii) motivations, including perceived health benefits, pro-environmental and sustainability benefits, perceived health risks, being adventurous/daring, curiosity, neophobia, and disgust; (iv) sociodemographic characteristics, including male gender and younger age. Recognizing differences in potential determinants across various APF sources is essential for designing interventions aimed at promoting APF uptake.

Keywords: systematic review; meta review; alternative protein food; motivation; socioeconomic status; COM-B model

A high-quality protein diet has well-established beneficial effects on human health, contributing to healthy weight management, improved metabolism, and healthy aging (Rodriguez, 2015). In developed countries, animal products, such as meat, eggs, and dairy, are the typical protein choices (Eat-Lancet Commission, 2022). However, meat and dairy production is among the strongest drivers of environmental degradation, threatening climate stability and ecosystems (Eat-Lancet Commission, 2022). Shifting from traditional, animal-based proteins to alternative proteins in daily diet may have positive effects on health: Replacing just 3% of animal protein with plant protein is associated with a decrease in overall mortality (10% in both men and women) and cardiovascular disease mortality (11-12% lower risk; Huang et al., 2020). Alternative protein food (APF) products include protein concentrates obtained during the processing of insects, krill, microbial biomass, mushrooms, fungi, or plants such as peas or rapeseed (Grossmann & Weiss, 2021). APF refers to sources with lower environmental impact compared to traditional protein sources (e.g., beef, pork, poultry, and animal dairy; Grossmann & Weiss, 2021). Thus, APF may exclude cultured meat as its environmental benefits are questioned (Grossmann & Weiss, 2021).

Socio-ecological models suggest that human behavior, including nutrition behavior, is influenced by individual-level determinants, socio-environmental factors, and policy factors (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Michie et al. (2011) proposed the Capability-Opportunity-Motivation (COM-B) model, capturing determinants from the individual-level (psychosocial), the social, and the physical environment. Since its inception, COM-B has been widely used by researchers and specialists from various disciplines (West & Michie, 2020). In accordance with the COM-B model, Capability (C) refers to an individual's physical and psychosocial abilities required to engage in a behavior, such as nutrition behavior. Opportunity (O) refers to an individual's physical and social environment, while motivation (M) includes reflective and automatic factors (Michie et al., 2011; West & Michie, 2022). Capability includes knowledge,

memory, attention processes, skills, or proficiencies acquired through repeated exposure or practice (Cane et al., 2012; McDonagh et al., 2018; Michie et al., 2011). Opportunity refers to the physical and social environment, social influences, social pressure norms, or perceptions of the built environment (McDonagh et al., 2018; Michie et al., 2011). Finally, motivation includes emotions that represent automatic processes, beliefs about consequences of behaviors, identity, values, or personality factors (Cane et al., 2012; McDonagh et al., 2018). Although the COM-B model addresses social and physical environment, it mainly focuses on individual-level determinants, akin to other behavior change models, suggesting that these determinants are the most proximal predictors of behavior change (Hagger et al., 2020; Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020). The COM-B model has already been applied in reviews of determinants of APF choices (Graça et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2022).

In addition to the predictors included in the COM-B, socio-ecological models of behavior change also highlight the role sociodemographic factors, such as age, gender, education, and income (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Sociodemographic characteristics are also crucial contextual factors to consider when designing health promotion interventions, ensuring the interventions align with the needs of the targeted population (see Context and Implementation of the Complex Interventions model; CICI; Pfadenhauer et al., 2019).

The rapidly increasing number of research on psychosocial determinants of intention (to buy or try) and actual purchase or intake of APF resulted in a growing number of reviews on this topic (e.g., Dagevos, 2020; Eckl et al., 2021; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Kauppi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Szenderák et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2023; Weinrich, 2019). Many of these reviews focus on specific APF sources, such as insect-based proteins only (Kröger et al., 2022). Other reviews combine evidence for various protein sources (e.g., Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021). Finally, a recent meta-review synthesized studies on meat reduction and alternative protein acceptance,

suggesting that several broad classes of determinants, e.g. “motives” or “emotions” may be associated with broadly defined reduction of intake of conventional meat and an increase of APF or in-vitro/lab-grown meat intake (Onwezen & Dagevos, 2023). Yet it remains unclear if determinants are common for dietary choices of APF from different sources, or if the determinants vary depending on the protein source (e.g. plant-based vs. insect-based APF). The existing reviews provide contradictory findings, for instance regarding the presence (or absence of) a significant association between knowledge and indicators of consumer choices of plant-based APF (e.g., Baiano, 2020; Eckl et al., 2021). Finally, it is important to identify the individual-level psychosocial determinants that have strong and consistent support across various contexts. Although several potential determinants have been identified in reviews, it is unclear which ones are well-supported and require further evidence.

The purpose of this meta-review (a systematic review of systematic, scoping, and realist reviews; Hennessy et al., 2019) was to synthesize the evidence for the associations between: (i) the individual-level psychosocial characteristics from the COM-B model (capabilities, perceived opportunities, and motivation) and sociodemographic factors from socio-ecological models of behavior change (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), such as age, gender, education, and income, and (ii) indicators of the individuals’ choices of alternative protein food. First, we investigate characteristics consistently identified in reviews as associated with indicators of consumer choice, suggesting that they can be considered strongly supported. Second, we studied specific and common individual-level characteristics that may be associated with a specific type of APF. We focused on distinguishing between psychosocial characteristics associated with dietary choices of plant-based and insect-based proteins, the two most frequently addressed protein types in APF research. Given that *individual-level psychosocial characteristics* are the focus of this study, our examination of opportunities addresses individuals’ perceptions of and beliefs about social and physical environment.

Methods

We conducted a meta-review integrating empirical evidence from existing systematic, realist, and scoping reviews. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Page et al., 2021) were applied. The study was preregistered with the PROSPERO database, no. CRD42023388694.

Search Strategy

A systematic search encompassing 11 databases of peer-reviewed journals (Academic Search Ultimate, PsycInfo, PsycArticles, Business Source Ultimate, Agricola, GreenFILE, Health Source: Nursing Academic Edition, SocINDEX, MEDLINE, MasterFILE Premier, Academic Research Source eJournals) was conducted using the EBSCO platform. The primary search was followed by searching the Web of Science and SCOPUS. Documents and articles published between the inception of the databases and March 2023 were included.

Furthermore, complementary non-systematic searches of published peer-reviewed papers in Google Scholar were conducted using the same keywords as for databases (for details see Supplemental Material). CORDIS and Open Research Europe (ORE) databases were also searched, using ‘alternative protein’ keywords (the alteration of the keywords was applied as CORDIS and ORE impose limits for the length of search strings, up to 50 characters). Finally, two researchers (FG, BTN) manually searched reference lists of reviews.

The systematic search applied a string with three groups of keywords that referred to: (1) indicators of APF choices or categories (e.g., accept* OR preference* OR willing* OR buy* OR purchas* OR choice* OR behavio* OR adopt* OR inten*) or indicators of individual-level determinants (e.g., behavio* OR belief* OR percep* OR motiv*); (2) alternative protein indicators (e.g., seaweed* OR alga* OR insect* OR lupin* OR legume* OR bean*); and (3) terms referring to review as a research method (e.g., meta-synthesis OR meta-review OR “synthesis of data” OR “critical analysis of the literature” OR metaanaly*

OR meta-analy* OR "meta analy*" OR "retrospective analysis" OR "qualitative analysis" OR "quantitative analysis"). For the full list of keywords, see Supplemental Material 1. The keywords were selected using existing reviews on APF (Mancini et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021) and research applying the COM-B model (Nguyen et al., 2022) and the CICI framework (Pfadenhauer et al., 2019). The list of keywords proposed by Hennessy et al. (2019) was used to identify reviews. For this meta-review, the chosen strategy was to use a broad, inclusive search string (e.g., applying multiple terms that represent the investigated factors, using only basic operators [AND, OR], and applying no specific limits) that could be used across the databases. The feasibility of the string was pretested across the databases before initiating the search.

Figure 1 presents the details of the data selection process. All identified abstracts were screened by two researchers (randomly assigned from a group of five researchers: HZ, EK, ZS, MS, AB) to elicit potentially relevant studies. Any conflicts related to the potential inclusion of a review were resolved through discussions with a fourth researcher (AL). Next, three researchers (AL and two researchers randomly assigned from a group of five: HZ, EK, ZS, MS, AB) independently read the full texts of the articles and determined their match with the inclusion criteria. The data search and evaluation resulted in the inclusion of 28 reviews.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following inclusion criteria were applied: (1) peer-reviewed systematic, scoping, or realist reviews of quantitative or qualitative studies; (2) reviews addressing APF from any sources, including alternative proteins that are plant-, fungi-, bacteria-, insect-, or krill-based, or addressing products combining meat- and plant-based proteins; (3) reviews testing associations between the individual-level determinants and APF choice indicators (e.g., intention to buy, intention to eat, actual intake, actual purchase, acceptability); and (4) reviews published in English language.

The exclusion criteria were: (1) original studies (i.e., research that focused on reporting new results of an original study), dissertations, protocols, conference materials, book chapters; (2) reviews focusing on the influence of APF intake on health or environmental outcomes, and reviews of policy guidelines; (3) reviews that focused solely on reducing meat intake without addressing the replacement of meat proteins with proteins from alternative sources; (4) reviews that focused on the intake of fruit/vegetable (or on a vegetarian diet), but did not include results related explicitly to APF; (5) reviews focusing solely on alternatively grown beef, poultry, or pork meat (e.g., laboratory-based, in-vitro grown); (6) reviews focusing on product characteristics, such as sustainability, production, packaging, and taste; and (7) reviews focusing solely on alternative proteins as supplements or as animal feed. In case a review focused on any of the latter goals (see points 2-7), but also discussed associations between individual-level characteristics and APF choices, respective sections dealing with links between these characteristics and APF choices were included.

Data Extraction and Coding

Data necessary for quality evaluation and assessing the risk of bias was extracted and coded by two reviewers (FG and BTN). In case of disagreements during this stage, a third researcher (AB or MS) achieved a resolution through arbitration. The remaining data extraction and coding were conducted by two researchers (HZ and AL). Disagreements were resolved using the consensus method (searching for rating errors, followed by discussion and arbitration by a third researcher, AB [Higgins et al., 2022]).

To address the study objectives, the following data were extracted (see Supplemental Material, Table S1 and S2): characteristics of reviews included (the number and design of original studies, populations studied, and countries where data were collected), general results of the reviews, types of APF analyzed, the APF choice indicators investigated, types of

individual-level characteristics investigated in the included review, and the associations between the APF choice indicators and the individual-level characteristics.

For details of the coding process, involving categorizing the reviews in terms of the types of APF and the individual-level psychosocial characteristics, see Supplemental Material (Table S2). According to the coding procedure, the *APF choice indicators* included (1) intention to buy, intention to eat, and intention to pay; (2) self-reported behavior, including self-reported intake, or “adoption” defined as including APF into one’s own daily diet (Rogers, 2003); (3) the actual performance of a behavior (e.g., the number of times the product was purchased); and (4) a broader category of “acceptance” of APF (cf. Onwezen et al. 2021), used in reviews summarizing purchase or intake-related behaviors and intentions.

Reviews were *coded as providing evidence for the association* (see reviews coded as “+” or “-“; Supplemental Material, Table S2) if the results of the included review reported significant associations between the choice indicator (e.g., intention to buy, pay, or eat, acceptability, and adoption) and individual-level characteristic (e.g., emotions such as disgust, curiosity). In case the results reported in the review were indicated as significant for some original studies, but not significant for other studies, the reviews were coded as providing mixed/non-significant evidence (see reviews coded as “0”; Supplemental Material, Table S2). As the included reviews did not separate results and conclusions for correlational studies versus experimental studies (comparing an experimental manipulation condition with a control condition), the causal vs. correlational character of the association was not coded.

Risk of Bias Assessment, Data Analysis Methods

The risk of bias and quality assessment of the included reviews was performed independently by two researchers (FG and BTN or AB and MS). The assessment was based on criteria from the ROBIS tool, which evaluates the risk of bias in systematic reviews (Whiting et al., 2016). Thresholds for categorizing reviews as having low, moderate, or high

risk of bias were defined following Whiting et al. (2016). The weighted Cohen's κ was calculated to assess inter-rater reliability. The values of κ indicated good agreement between raters, with $\kappa = 0.88$ (95 CI: [0.74, 1.00]).

We used a narrative synthesis method to analyze collected data based on the four cornerstones for the narrative synthesis developed by the UK Economic and Social Research Council (Campbell et al., 2019). For details, see Supplemental Material.

The obtained results were summarized as *providing preliminary support* or *providing strong support*. In case the individual-level characteristics were addressed in $k \geq 3$ reviews and at least between $\geq 51\%$ and $\leq 66\%$ of included reviews indicated a significant association (in the same direction), then the association was considered *preliminarily supported* by the analyzed data. The associations were also coded as providing preliminary support when only two included reviews addressed the respective associations, with both indicating consistent significant associations (in the same direction). The association between an individual-level characteristic and an APF choice indicator was considered *strongly supported* if $> 66\%$ of included reviews ($k \geq 3$) indicated a significant association in the same direction (e.g., three out of four reviews studying respective associations indicated positive links between the two indices). These thresholds did not account for the number or quality of the original studies included in respective reviews. Similar thresholds were applied in previous meta-reviews addressing nutrition behaviors (e.g., Horodyska et al., 2015).

Results

Preliminary Results

A total of $k = 28$ reviews were included. The reviews reported findings from 1,014 original studies (six reviews did not provide information about the number of included studies). Supplemental Material (Table S1 and S2) presents the details of the populations

analyzed, designs, APF investigated, and psychosocial characteristics associated with APF choices.

The risk of bias scores obtained using ROBIS are reported in Supplemental Material, Table S3. Out of the total number of reviews included, 53.6% ($k = 15$) were evaluated as representing a low risk of bias across five criteria of ROBIS, 3.6% ($k = 1$) was considered to represent low risk across four criteria, and 3.6% ($k = 1$) had low risk in three criteria. The remaining 39.3% ($k = 11$) of the reviews were of unclear risk in ≥ 3 criteria.

Main Findings

COM-B Capabilities: Skills and Formal and Informal Knowledge

Skills. Four out of four (100%) reviews focusing on consumers' *cooking skills*, found that higher perceived cooking skills were associated with a higher level of acceptance or adoption of *plant-based APF* (Eckl et al., 2021; Graça et al., 2019; He et al., 2020; Onwezen et al., 2021). Additionally, one review addressing *APF from various sources* also reported similar findings (Nguyen et al., 2022).

A capability to replace proteins from animal sources with APF, in particular, *perceived easiness and convenience of replacing meat with APF*, were associated with higher intention to buy and acceptance of *APF from various sources* (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023) and a higher likelihood of self-reported intake adopting *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019). However, the findings referring to *insect-based APF* were mixed, with one review of high quality yielding null results for intention to buy/pay/eat *insect-based APF* (Wassmann et al., 2021), and two out of three reviews (66%) indicating associations between acceptance, self-reported intake, and adoption (Florença et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021).

Purchase activism, defined as the willingness to take action that impacts the marketplace and affects the food system via active food choices, was associated with intention to buy *insect-based APF* in one review (Kröger et al., 2022).

Two reviews that investigated if *mindfulness* practices (practicing an ability to be in the present moment through non-judgmental attention and awareness) are associated with the acceptance of *insect-based APF* indicated null or inconsistent findings in the original research (Dagevos, 2020; Kröger et al., 2022).

Formal knowledge (education-related) and informal knowledge (sense of familiarity, related to previous exposure). *Formal knowledge* (knowing nutrition values, evidence-based effects of protein intake on individual health and environment; cf. Eckl et al., 2021) exhibits inconsistent associations with the intention to buy/pay or acceptance of *plant-based APF* (two reviews; Baiano, 2020; Eckl et al., 2021). Furthermore, formal knowledge was unrelated or inconsistently related to the acceptance of *APF from various sources* (Giordano et al., 2017). One review addressing *mushroom/fungi APF* (De Cianni et al., 2023) indicated positive associations between formal knowledge and acceptance of APF.

In case of *insect-based APF*, nine out of ten (90%) reviews suggest that there is a positive association between formal knowledge and intention to buy/pay/try, acceptance, and adoption of insects as diet components (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Batat & Peter, 2020; Eckl et al., 2021; Florença et al., 2022; Kauppi et al., 2019; Mancini et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Weinrich, 2019). One review suggests mixed effects or no association between formal knowledge and acceptance of insect-based APF (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). Importantly, formal knowledge may increase the intention to buy, but as the intention to eat is still low, it is unlikely that mere formal knowledge will prompt people to actually adopt insect-based APF into a daily diet (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021). Additionally, one review suggests no direct effects of formal knowledge, but a moderated association (Dagevos, 2020). Specifically, formal knowledge (e.g., an education intervention) may influence insect-based APF intake, but only for consumers who are interested in the nutritional, health, or sustainability benefits of APF (Dagevos, 2020).

The process of acquiring *informal knowledge* (defined as multiple exposures to the product, resulting in perceived familiarity, cf. Eckl et al., 2021) seems to be consistently associated with APF choices. Five out of five reviews (100%) addressing *plant-based APF* suggested that acquiring informal knowledge is associated with intention to buy, acceptance, self-reported intake, or adoption (Baiano, 2020; Graça et al., 2019; He et al., 2020; Onwezen et al., 2021; Szenderák et al., 2022). Four out of four (100%) reviews addressing acceptance or adoption of *APF from various sources* also suggest a positive association with perceived familiarity/exposure (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Nguyen et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022). Significant positive associations were also found for *mushroom-based APF* (one review; De Cianni, 2023).

Furthermore, 12 out of 12 (100%) reviews suggest that informal knowledge is associated with intention to buy, pay, try, acceptance, self-reported intake, and adoption of *insect-based APF* (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Knaupi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Mancini et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Onwezen et al., 2021; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2022). However, three reviews indicated some limitations for these associations. For example, the type of product may be important: Including insect-based proteins to develop popular food products (hamburgers) may be the most effective strategy to increase acceptance (Mancini et al., 2019). The association with insect-based APF acceptance may be significant for the number of exposures, whereas it may be non-significant for feelings of familiarity (Wassmann et al., 2021). Familiarity and exposure may be sufficient triggers to try insect-based APF, but not sufficient to maintain it as a regular food habit (Dagevos, 2020).

COM-B Opportunities: Perceptions of the Environment

Perceptions of social norms and cultural norms. *Positive social norms* (beliefs that APF is accepted by their peers, family, or important others) were consistently associated with

APF choices across included reviews. Two out of two (100%) reviews addressing social norms and *plant-based APF* indicated that positive social norms are associated with intention to eat and acceptance of these types of foods (Graça et al., 2019; Onwezen et al., 2021). Furthermore, these associations were also positive and significant across three out of three reviews (100%) addressing acceptance of *APF from various sources* (Giordano et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023) and in two out of two (100%) reviews addressing *mushroom/fungi-based APF* (De Cianni et al., 2023; Eckl et al., 2021).

Regarding *insect-based APF*, 12 out of 12 (100%) reviews indicated significant associations between positive social norms and higher intention to try and to eat (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Kauppi et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Wassmann et al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021), acceptance of (Kröger et al., 2022; Mancini et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021), or adoption of a diet including such proteins (Florença et al., 2022).

Three reviews indicated that other psychosocial characteristics were consistently positively associated with APF choices. *Social support from family and friends* to follow a specific diet was associated with higher self-reported intake of *plant-based APF* (one review; Graça et al., 2019). Having a *positive social image and perceived high sociability of eating meat* was associated with lower intention to eat *APF from various sources* (one review; Nguyen et al., 2022). Additionally, perceiving *eating meat as a positive social norm* was associated with a lower intake of *plant-based APF* (He et al., 2020).

Perceived cultural norms, referring to the perception that APF fits the cuisine of a region or food culture/dietary patterns typical of a region, were associated with stronger intention to try, acceptance, self-reported intake, and adoption of a diet including *insect-based APF* (Batat & Peter, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Giordano et al., 2017; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Kauppi et al., 2019; Mancini et al., 2019; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi

et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). In sum, ten out of ten (100%) reviews suggest significant associations. The same was true in the case of three reviews on *APF from various sources* (De Cianni, 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022). In line with these findings, *perceived incompatibility with local food* was associated with a lower likelihood of adopting *APF from various sources* (Weinrich, 2019).

Safety and trust in the APF food system stakeholders. *Distrust in technology used in the development of food products* (also known as food technology neophobia) is associated with a lower level of intention to buy and acceptance of *plant-based APF* (two reviews; Onwezen et al., 2021; Szenderák et al., 2022). Additionally, distrust in technology is negatively associated with the intention to buy/pay, acceptance, and adoption of *insect-based APF* (four reviews; Florença et al., 2022; Kröger et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2020; Wendt & Weinrich, 2023). Three other reviews that addressed *APF from various sources* also found negative associations between distrust in technology and intention to buy and acceptance (Eckl et al., 2021; Giordano et al., 2017; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022).

Perceived safety of food production, retail, storage, etc. is another belief that has been investigated in the context of APF. Three reviews addressing this issue indicated that lower perceived safety was associated with lower acceptance of either *insect-based APF* (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021), *plant-based APF* (Baiano, 2020), or *APF from various sources* (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022).

Finally, three reviews provided insights into the role of *low trust in/uncertainty of research, science, independent food promoters, or organizations*. All three reviews (100%) concluded that low trust is associated with lower acceptance of *APF from various sources* (Giordano et al., 2017; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022).

COM-B Motivation: Beliefs, Attitudes, Emotions

Beliefs about health benefits and health risks of alternative proteins. All reviews (eight out of eight, 100%) referring to *health benefits as a motive* in consumers' decisions to choose *plant-based APF* products indicate positive associations. Individuals reporting higher beliefs in the healthiness of APF, and positive health consequences of eating *plant-based APF*, reported stronger intentions to buy and consume, declared acceptance or adoption of *plant-based APF* (Eckl et al., 2021; Graça et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Szenderák et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Weinrich, 2019). *Perceiving high nutritional value* of plant-based food was associated with higher acceptance of *plant-based APF* (one review; Wang et al., 2023). Beliefs that switching to a meatless plant-only diet is *a health risk* was related to a lower likelihood of an adoption of *plant-based APF* (one review; He et al., 2020). Finally, *beliefs about the unhealthiness of novel food* were associated with lower acceptability of novel *plant-based APF* (one review; Baiano, 2020).

Regarding *mushroom-based APF*, only one review addressed this issue and found that consumers' beliefs about positive health consequences were associated with higher intake of respective APF (De Cianni et al., 2023).

In case of *insect-based APF*, two high-quality reviews indicated mixed or non-significant associations between *perceived health benefits* and intention to pay/eat and acceptance of insect-based APF (Kröger et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2021). Five out of eight (62.5%) reviews suggest significant associations between perceived health benefits and *insect-based APF choices* (Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Toti et al., 2020; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). Furthermore, two reviews addressing perceived *nutritional value* of APF indicated mixed/non-significant associations between perceptions of nutritional value and acceptance of insect-based APF (Wang et al., 2023; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). The mixed results for links between perceived healthiness and insect-based APF are consistent with associations reported for beliefs that intake of insect-based food constitutes a

health risk. Five out of five (100%) reviews suggested that perceiving *insect intake-related health risks* was related to lower levels of intention to buy/pay, acceptance, and adoption of an *insect-based APF* (Batat & Peter, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2021).

Three reviews that addressed *various types of APF* indicated that perceived healthiness or *perceived health benefits* are associated with the intention to buy, intention to eat, and acceptability of APF (Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021, Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023). Similarly, *perceived health risks* were indicated as a barrier to the intake of various types of novel APF products (Giordano et al., 2017). Beliefs about the *healthiness of meat* were a barrier to the intention to eat various APF (one review; Nguyen et al., 2022).

Beliefs about environmental impact, sustainability, and animal welfare. *Pro-environmental and sustainability-related beliefs* and motives were studied as correlates of plant-based and mushroom/fungi-based APF choices. Three in four (75%) reviews indicated that such reasons are related to higher intention to try/eat, acceptance, and self-reported intake of the *plant-based APF* (Eckl et al., 2021; Graça et al., 2019; Onwezen et al., 2021), one showed mixed findings for intention to buy, eat, and try (Szenderák et al., 2020). One review indicated positive associations for intention to buy, eat, and try *mushroom/fungi-based APF* (De Cianni et al., 2023). Regarding reviews addressing *various APF*, including plants and insect-based, two yielded positive associations with pro-environmental/sustainability motives and intention to eat, try, acceptance, and self-reported intake (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Weinrich, 2019) and one indicated mixed/null findings for intention to try, eat, and self-reported intake (Nguyen et al., 2022). Nguyen et al. (2022) suggested that the potential explanation for inconsistent results may refer to the weakness of the associations with self-reported intake indicators, which do not translate to the actual purchase.

High *climate change skepticism* was related to a lower likelihood of self-reported intake and adoption of *plant-based APF* (one review; Graça et al., 2019).

Regarding *pro-environmental and sustainability beliefs*, the pattern of associations is mixed for the *insect-based APF*. Six reviews concluded that there are positive associations between environment/sustainability-related beliefs and intention to buy and try, acceptance, self-reported intake, and adoption of insect-based APF (Florença et al., 2022; Mancini et al., 2019; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et al., 2021). Five reviews indicated mixed, inconclusive findings (Dagevos, 2020; Kröger et al., 2022; Mina et al., 2023; Weinrich, 2019; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021) for intention to pay and try, and acceptance. In sum, 6 out of 11 reviews (54.5%) supported the associations.

Animal welfare, ethical and moral motives, conservative values, and religion.

Regarding *concerns about animal welfare and empathy* towards animals three out of three (100%) reviews consistently showed that welfare beliefs are related to a higher likelihood of adoption of *plant-based APF* (Eckl et al., 2021; Graça et al., 2019; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023). An association between animal welfare concerns and higher self-reported intake/adoption of *insect-based APF* was indicated in one review only (Florença et al., 2022).

Regarding reviews investigating *more general moral and ethical motives* (i.e., not only related to animal welfare), reviews suggested that *moral disengagement* was related to a lower likelihood of adopting *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019). Furthermore, indicating moral and ethical motives as guiding dietary choices was related to the acceptance of plant-based APF (Onwezen et al., 2021) and to a stronger intention to pay, eat, and adopt *insect-based APF* (Wassmann et al., 2021).

Following conservative views or values and being religious was unrelated to the adoption of *plant-based APF* in nutrition behaviors in two reviews (Graça et al., 2019; Szenderák et al., 2022). *Religiousness* was unrelated to acceptance of *insect-based APF*,

except for findings from India (probably related to beliefs about the holiness of certain animals; Kröger et al., 2022). In contrast, Onwezen et al. (2021) suggested associations between stronger conservative beliefs and weaker acceptance of *APF from various sources*. The discrepancy may result from different conceptualizations of conservativeness, e.g., either as a construct closer to following religious codes of conduct or as a construct related to environmental skepticism, which in turn may be related to lower acceptance of APF.

Emotions. Reviews addressing positive emotions focused entirely on *insect-based APF*. *Feeling adventurous, daring, excitement accompanying sensation seeking, and positive emotion excitement* were consistently associated with the intention to eat and try, acceptance, and adoption of *insect-based APF*, as indicated in eight out of eight (100%) reviews (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Kauppi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). One review highlighted that these associations may be typical of young men (Kauppi et al., 2019). In six out of six (100%) reviews, *curiosity* showed positive associations with the intention to try, acceptance, and adoption of *insect-based APF* (Ardoin, 2021; Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Toti et al., 2020; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021).

Food *neophilia* (liking new types of food) was associated with acceptance of *insect-based APF* in two out of two (100%) reviews (Dagevos, 2020; Kröger et al., 2022).

Attachment and positive emotions towards meat were related to lower intention to eat, likelihood of a purchase, self-reported intake, and adoption of *plant-based APF* in two out of three (66%) reviews addressing this type of protein (Graça et al., 2019; He et al., 2020), and in one review addressing *APF from various sources* (Nguyen et al., 2022). One review addressing intention to eat, the likelihood of actual purchase, or the adoption of *plant-based APF* yielded inconclusive results (Szenderák et al., 2022). Only one review, albeit of high

quality, tested associations between meat attachment and adoption of *insect-based APF*, concluding that findings are inconsistent (Kröger et al., 2022).

Other meat-related emotions, namely *worry and guilt towards eating meat* were associated with higher self-reported intake or adoption of *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019) or *APF from various sources* (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Food neophobia, which refers to aversion or anxiety experienced when exposed to novel food, was addressed in three reviews of *plant-based APF*. Overall, the results suggest food neophobia may be relevant, with two out of three (66%) reviews yielding conclusions about negative associations with acceptance and self-reported intake of plant-based APF (Graça et al., 2019; Onwezen et al., 2021) and one indicating non-significant or inconsistent relationships with self-reported intake (Szenderák et al., 2022). Two reviews that addressed acceptance of *APF from various sources* suggested that APF acceptance is associated with lower levels of food neophobia (Eckl et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022). Regarding *insect-based APF*, the findings consistently show significant associations (twelve out of twelve reviews, 100%) between low neophobia and intention to pay, try, eat, acceptance, self-reported intake, and early adoption of this type of APF (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Batat & Peter, 2020; Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Kröger et al., 2022; Mina et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021).

Disgust, including the general emotion of disgust, food disgust, and insect disgust, is related to lower intention to pay or try, acceptance, and adoption of *insect-based APF*. The associations were consistent and found in 11 out of 11 reviews (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Batat & Peter, 2020; Deroy et al., 2015; Florença et al., 2022; Kröger et al., 2022; Mina et al., 2023; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et

al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). Only one review addressed acceptance of *plant-based APF* (algae) and indicated negative associations with disgust (Onwezen et al., 2021).

Self-efficacy and personality. *Self-efficacy beliefs* and perceived behavioral control are two closely related constructs that refer to individual's beliefs about the ability to act and control one's own behavior (Bandura, 1997). Higher self-efficacy or beliefs about behavioral control were associated with self-reported intake or adoption of *plant-based APF* in one review (Graça et al., 2019). Higher self-efficacy was related to self-reported intake and acceptance of *APF from various sources* (two out of two reviews; Giordano et al., 2017; Onwezen et al., 2021), and a higher intention to try, buy, and acceptance of *insect-based APF* (two out of two reviews; Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Kröger et al., 2022).

Only two reviews provide information on any personality traits that are associated with consumers' APF choices. *Openness*, referring to intellectual curiosity, and challenging authority, was related to the intention to try and initial adoption of *APF from various sources* (Nguyen et al., 2022). *Openness and extraversion* were also related to the intention to pay and eat *insect-based APF* products (Kröger et al., 2022). However, in the case of *neuroticism* and *agreeableness*, mixed or null findings between intention to pay and eat were observed for *insect-based APF* (one review; Kröger et al., 2022).

Individual-level Context Determinants: The Role of Sociodemographic Characteristics

Gender. Three out of five (60%) reviews suggested that *women* are more likely to report an intention to eat, higher acceptability, or greater intake of *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023). Two reviews suggested inconclusive findings for intention to buy or pay and acceptance for plant-based APF, depending on gender (Nguyen et al., 2022; Szenderák et al., 2022). Mixed or non-significant associations were also reported in two out of two (100%) reviews addressing the intake of *fungi or mushroom-based APF* (De Cianni et al., 2023; Eckl et al., 2021). Two reviews

suggested that gender operates forming interactions with age: (i) acceptance of plant-based APF is higher only among older women (Szenderák et al., 2022); (ii) educational interventions may be effective in influencing intention to adopt plant-based APF among younger women only (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Regarding *insect-based APF*, the results are more consistent. In 9 out of 12 reviews *men* were more willing to pay or eat, reported higher acceptance, and were more likely to adopt *insect-based APF* (Dagevos, 2020; Florença et al., 2022; Kauppi et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Wassmann et al., 2021; Weinrich, 2019; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). No associations or mixed effects were found in three reviews, addressing intention to eat and acceptance of insect-based APF (Mancini et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020). Additionally, three reviews suggested that gender forms interactions with other psychosocial characteristics predicting choices of insect-based APF: (i) its effect on acceptance depends on the type of insects or the types of food processing involved (Kröger et al., 2022); (ii) the effect of education interventions on intention to adopt a diet may be significant among younger men (Kauppi et al., 2019).

Age. Regarding *plant-based APF*, *younger age* was associated with higher intake and more frequent trying APF in three out of four (75%) reviews (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Szenderák et al., 2022), while one review reported mixed or non-significant findings for intention to try and acceptance of plant-based APF (Graça et al., 2019). Similarly, mixed or non-significant findings with age were reported in two out of two (100%) reviews addressing acceptance and intake of *mushroom/fungi-based APF* (De Cianni et al., 2023, Eckl et al., 2021). Finally, one review addressing acceptance of *APF from various sources* indicated mixed results with age (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Regarding *insect-based APF*, significant associations with younger age were reported in the majority (7 out of 10, 70%) of the reviews, addressing acceptance, trying, and adoption

of such diet (Dagevos, 2020; Eckl et al., 2021; Florença et al., 2022; Mina et al., 2023; Toti et al., 2020; Weinrich, 2019; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). However, two reviews indicated mixed or nonsignificant associations between intention to pay or eat and acceptance (Kröger et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2021). One review highlighted that among adolescents, older are more likely to try insect-based APF than younger adolescents/children (Kröger et al., 2022).

Education. Three out of three (100%) reviews suggested that *higher education* is associated with indicators of acceptance and self-reported intake of *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Szenderák et al., 2022). One review addressing *various types of APF*, including plant- and insect-based indicated mixed or non-significant results (Nguyen et al., 2022). Notably the associations may be negative (higher education- less likely APF choices) in developing countries in Africa or Asia (Szenderák et al., 2022). Reviews on acceptance of *mushroom/fungi-based APF* and education yielded mixed findings or no association (2 out of 2 reviews, 100%; De Cianni et al., 2023; Eckl et al., 2021).

Regarding *insect-based APF*, only three out of seven reviews addressing this issue showed that higher education is associated with acceptance or early adoption of insect-based APF (Dagevos, 2020; Mina et al., 2023; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021). Four reviews suggested mixed or non-significant findings for intention to buy or pay, or acceptance of this type of APF (Eckl et al., 2021; Kauppi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Wassmann et al., 2021).

Income. Regarding *higher income* levels, two out of three (66%) reviews found significant correlations between this characteristic and the adoption of *plant-based APF* (Graça et al., 2019; Siddiqui, Bahid et al., 2022). One review indicated no associations with intention to pay or intake of plant-based APF (Szenderák et al., 2022). There were no associations between income and acceptance of *mushroom/fungi-based APF* (one review; Eckl et al., 2021). One review suggested that the adoption of *insect-based APF* is associated with higher income (Florença et al., 2022).

Psychosocial Predictors of Plant-Based APF Versus Predictors of Insect-Based APF

Table 1 provides a synthesis of findings that provide evidence for (1) preliminary support (51-66% of $k \geq 3$ reviews addressing the respective associations indicated significant effects) or (2) strong support (> 66% of $k \geq 3$ reviews addressing the respective associations indicated significant effects) for the relationships between individual-level characteristics and APF choice indicators. In particular, *preliminary or strong support* was obtained for the relationships between *plant-based APF* choices and the individual-level characteristics from the COM-B model, including: (1) Capabilities, such as cooking skills, exposure to APF and related familiarity; (2) perceived Opportunities, including positive social norms, low distrust in technology used in the development of APF; (3) Motivations, such as perceived health benefits, pro-environmental and sustainability benefits, animal welfare/empathy towards animals, low attachment towards meat, low food neophobia. Female gender, younger age, higher education, and higher income also obtained preliminary or strong support as characteristics associated with *plant-based APF* choices (Table 1). For characteristics that received *strong support*, see Figure 2, the top panel.

Regarding *insect-based APF* choices, *preliminary support or strong support* was obtained for associations with COM-B-based individual-level characteristics: (i) Capabilities referring to formal knowledge about APF, exposure to APF, and related familiarity; (ii) Perceived Opportunities, referring to positive social norms, perceived positive cultural norms accepting APF, and low distrust in technology used in development of APF; (iii) Motivations, such as perceived health benefits, pro-environmental and sustainability benefits, low perceived health risks, feelings of being adventurous, daring, excitement, emotion of curiosity, liking new food (neophilia), low neophobia, low disgust, and high self-efficacy beliefs. Male gender and younger age are also associated with *insect-based APF* choices (Table 1). For characteristics that received *strong support*, see Figure 2, the bottom panel.

Discussion

This study provides a theory-based synthesis of evidence concerning the individual-level characteristics that are consistently associated with indicators of APF choices. The results highlight both similarities and differences in association patterns based on the source of APF, specifically comparing plant-based and insect-based APF choices.

Considering the three domains of the COM-B model (McDonagh et al., 2018; Michie et al., 2011), the *Capability* domain has received the least attention in the identified reviews. Multiple exposures to APF products and related feelings of familiarity emerged as the common individual-level correlate of plant-based and insect-based APF choices. Thus, increasing exposure to APF in the food environment could be an initial strategy to increase awareness and consumption of APF (Stiles et al., 2021). Cooking skills, the second strongly supported characteristics from the *Capability* domain, although the support was obtained for plant-based APF only. Future interventions promoting APF intake may include cooking workshops at schools or other public institutions to enhance cooking skills. Besides, they can provide the opportunity for exposure to APF, and thus increase the familiarity with these products. Such workshops may also leverage the “IKEA effect”, where active participation in the preparation process increases liking of the prepared food, which then increases the intake (Radtke et al., 2019). Improving cooking skills may also serve as a “mastery experience” (e.g., “I have done it successfully!”). This may, in turn, enhance consumers’ self-efficacy referring to the ability to adopt a regular APF intake (Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020).

Across individuals’ perceptions and beliefs about social and physical environment, which constitute the *Opportunity* domain of the COM-B model (Cane et al., 2012; McDonagh et al., 2018; Michie et al., 2011), consistent evidence emerged for positive social norms, cultural norms, and distrust in technology used in insect-based APF development. Previous research has shown that when individuals were asked how they would eat insect-

based APF products, their response was “with either an expert” or “with someone who knows how to cook them” (Bisconsin-Júnior, 2022). Identifying such experts who are relevant role models for the consumers may enhance consumers’ confidence in insect-based APF as socially approved products and thus increase adoption of respective products.

Cultural norms referring to the alignment between the protein source and the culinary traditions or food environment in a respective country or culture were also identified as relevant determinants of insect-based APF choices. Strong food culture and culinary traditions, promoting animal-based products by awarding Protected Designation of Origin certificates, may hinder the initiation of APF consumption (Mancini & Antonioli, 2022). Previous research suggested that Italy, a country with strong culinary norms, has low readiness to adopt insect-based APF (Mancini & Antonioli, 2022).

Regarding insect-based APF, another significant psychosocial characteristic from the *Opportunity* domain is a lack of trust in the technology used to develop alternative proteins. Distrust may be associated with limited knowledge about insect-based APF (a *Capability* factor hindering APF intake) and negative emotion-related factors (such as neophobia, a *Motivation* factor). Previous research has suggested that high trust in actions of food system stakeholders, including food producers, scientists, and consumer organizations, may be considered one of the key potential determinants of choices of various novel types of food (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020). Our study points out that the trust factor may be specifically relevant for insect-based APF.

Regarding the individual-level psychosocial factors from the *Opportunity* domain as correlates of plant-based APF choices, we obtained preliminary (for plant-based APF) or strong support (for insect-based APF) for positive social norms. The fact that social norms obtained “only” preliminary support for plant-based APF may be explained by earlier research indicating that social norms may operate differently within certain subgroups. For

example, among meat-eating men the presence of other men (e.g., in restaurants) may be a barrier to choosing plant-based APF products due to the influence of masculinity norms (Bogueva et al., 2022). In contrast, women who frequently dine out in restaurants with friends are more likely to have positive social norms towards plant-based APF, which in turn is associated with higher plant-based APF choices (Weinrich & Elshiewy, 2023).

The *Motivation* domain of the COM-B model yielded the largest number of strongly supported factors, with most of these factors forming a distinctive set of psychosocial correlates either of plant-based APF or insect-based APF. Perceived health benefits constitute the only characteristic from this domain, that was strongly supported for both plant-based and insect-based APF. Previous research has argued that addressing health benefits in promoting the consumption of insect-based APF may have a limited effect due to the temporally distant character of health-related goals (Berger et al., 2018). Additionally, for insect-based APF, health risks and related negative emotions, such as food neophobia or distrust, emerged as strongly supported correlates. Previous research has shown that beliefs about health-related risks may have an emotional component of fear or anxiety (Ruiter et al., 2001). Fear and anxiety are central components of general, food-specific, or insect-specific neophobia. As a result, health risk perceptions and neophobia may be interconnected, creating a vicious cycle that reduces the likelihood of adopting novel or insect-based APF foods. Beliefs about higher health risks may also be related to lower individual familiarity with novel APF products (Tuorila & Hartmann, 2020).

Our findings within the *Motivational* domain of the COM-B model highlight the crucial role of automatic regulatory processes in the adoption of insect-based APF into consumers' diets. Besides negative emotions, our findings underscore the pivotal role of positive emotions such as curiosity or feeling adventurous, daring, seeking excitement, and sensations in the adoption of dietary shifts, including insect-based APF. These findings may

have practical implications. Interventions prompting curiosity and excitement should be implemented, accounting for a presence of experts whose knowledge and skills would guarantee safety and low health risks. Food events/festivals may constitute an intervention setting where curiosity may prompt individuals to try insect-based APF. Recent research has indicated that food festivals are the preferred setting for trying APF (Motoki et al., 2022).

In contrast to insect-based APF, a different set of *Motivation*-related factors emerged as strongly supported correlates of plant-based APF. These factors include pro-environmental and sustainability beliefs, and empathy towards animals. Interventions promoting plant-based APF should target sustainability beliefs or animal welfare issues, whereas interventions promoting insect-based APF should address different motivation-related determinants, such as curiosity, or familiarize consumers with insect-based food to reduce their neophobia.

Finally, our meta-review points towards the specificity of the sociodemographic factors associated with plant-based and insect-based APF choices. For insect-based APF, men are more likely to opt for such products, whereas the education level is unlikely to hinder or promote insect-based APF choices. These findings are of particular relevance, as men and lower education groups are in need for nutrition interventions but are often harder to reach (Darmon & Drewnowski, 2008). For plant-based APF, the correlates of consumer choices include higher education (a strongly supported factor) and female gender (preliminary support). Although men are less likely to choose plant-based APF than women, men may be influenced by their female partners and choose plant-based APF when dining out with romantic partners, according to prior research (Bogueva et al., 2022).

One important finding is the relative lack of research on individual-level psychosocial characteristics of actual trying or actual intake of APF. The majority of reviews focus on research addressing intentions and acceptability; self-reported intake is measured less frequently, and experimental research measuring the actual intake of APF is rare. Further

evidence confirming the links between the psychosocial characteristics discussed in our review, and acts of purchase, trying, or regular intake of APF is needed.

Implications and limitations

The findings of this meta-review have some implications for practice. Awareness-raising campaigns, educational interventions, and other actions promoting the widespread acceptance of APF products requires addressing various characteristics of consumers and accounting for the source of APF. Such tailoring may result in a better alignment between the characteristics of target populations and the type of the promoted APF product, and consequently mainstreaming APF choices. For example, a marketing strategy involving sustainability-oriented female consumer models and curiosity-oriented male consumer models might promote plant-and insect-based APF choices.

Beyond its strengths, the present study has several limitations. The majority of original studies analyzed in the included reviews provide evidence for correlations between individual-level “determinants” and the indicators of APF choices. Thus, any causal conclusions should be made with caution as such evidence is still limited. The category of the consumer choice indicators was very broad and varied from intentions to actual intake. Additionally, the coding of the consumer-choice indicators relied on the specificity of the operationalization and description of respective factors in the included reviews. The limited number of reviews addressing APF other than plant-based or insect-based imposes limitations to drawing conclusions regarding the specificity of correlates that may be significant, e.g., in case of fungi- mushroom-, or microbial-based APF. The results of the quality evaluation indicated that only half of reviews presented a low risk of bias. These findings should inspire a consideration of the insufficient quality of many reviews and potentially flawed results. Furthermore, included reviews were heterogeneous in terms of target groups and settings, therefore any conclusions should be treated as preliminary. The conclusions of any meta-

review may be biased if there is an overlap in the original studies analyzed in the included reviews (Hennessy et al., 2019). The heterogeneity of the aims of reviews included in this meta-review reduces the likelihood of such overlap, yet some overlap is undoubtedly expected. The effects of the overlap were not tested systematically. In line with previous reviews (Horodyska et al., 2015), we used a threshold of 66% as indicating strong support and 50% as indicating preliminary support for an analyzed determinant. The distinction between these two thresholds is arbitrary and the pattern of the associations should be confirmed further in a meta-analysis of original research presenting quantitative results. As a limited number of included reviews reported quantitative results for any of the determinants, conducting a meta-analysis was not feasible.

Concluding, this study offers a theory-based synthesis of evidence on individual-level psychosocial determinants of APF choices. Our findings may inform policymakers, food producers, researchers and other actors within the food supply chain, of the need for accounting for individual's capabilities, motivations, sociodemographic characteristics, and perceived opportunities, when making plans for the development of programs promoting APF intake. Finally, it underscores substantial differences in determinants associated with plant-based APF choices compared to insect-based APF choices.

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Figure captions

Figure 1

The Data Selection Process

Note. * Academic Search Ultimate, PsycInfo, PsycArticles Business Source Ultimate, Agricola, GreenFILE, Health Source: Nursing Academic Edition, SocINDEX, MEDLINE, MasterFILE Premier, Academic Research Source eJournals

Figure 1

Summary of the Individual-Level Characteristics Associated with Plant-Based Alternative Protein Food Choices (the Upper Panel) and Insect-Based Alternative Protein Food Choices (the Bottom Panel): Characteristics Strongly Support in the Meta-Review

Figure 1

Figure 2

Table 1

Summary of the Meta-Review Findings for Individual-Level Determinants of Alternative Protein Food (APF) Choices by Consumers

Individual determinants of APF choice (domains according to the COM-B model and the CICI framework)	Plant-based APF	Insect-based APF	Mushroom-/fungi-based APF	APF from various sources (incl. plants, insects, proteins from other sources)
COM- B: CAPABILITIES				
Cooking skills	+++			?
Easiness to replace meat and convenience to replace meat	?	++?	++?	?
Purchase activism		?		
Mindfulness training		--?		
Formal knowledge	0	+++	?	?
Multiple exposures to APF, perceived familiarity	+++	+++	?	+++
COM-B: OPPORTUNITIES				
Positive social norms	++?	+++	++?	+++
Social support from family and friends	?			
Positive social image and perceived high sociability of eating meat				?
Eating meat as a positive social norm	?			
Positive perceived cultural norms		+++		+++
Perceived incompatibility with local food				?
Distrust in technology used in APF development	--?	---		---
Perceived unsafety of the food production, retail, storage	?	?		?
Low trust in/uncertainty of research, science, independent food promoters or organizations				---
COM-B: MOTIVATION				
Perceived health benefits/ healthiness	+++	+++		
Perceived high nutritional value	?	0		
Health risk	?	---		?
Pro-environmental and sustainability benefit	+++	++?	?	++?
Climate change skepticism	?		?	
Animal welfare/empathy towards animals	+++	?		
Moral disengagement	?			

Individual determinants of APF choice (domains according to the COM-B model and the CICI framework)	Plant-based APF	Insect-based APF	Mushroom-/fungi-based APF	APF from various sources (incl. plants, insects, proteins from other sources)
Moral and ethical motives	?	?		
Worldview conservatism	0			
Religiousness		?		
Feeling adventurous, daring, excitement accompanying sensation-seeking		+++		
Curiosity		+++		
Neophilia (liking new food)		++?		
Attachment and positive emotions towards meat	--?			?
Worry or guilt towards eating meat	?			?
Food neophobia	--?	---		--?
Disgust	?	---		
Self-efficacy	?	++?	?	++?
Openness		?		?
Neuroticism		?		
Agreeableness		?		
CONTEXT: SOCIOECONOMIC DETERMINANTS				
Female gender	++?	---	00?	
Younger age	+++	+++	00?	
Education	+++	00	0	?
Income	++?	?	?	?

Note. APF = alternative protein food; +++ = results indicating strong support with > 66% of positive association reviews ($k \geq 3$; e.g., 3 out of 3, 3 out of 4 etc.); --- = results indicating strong support for > 66% of negative association reviews ($k \geq 3$, e.g., 3 out of 3, 3 out of 4 etc.); ++? = results indicating preliminary support between 51% and 66% of reviews show positive association ($k \geq 3$, e.g., 2 out of 3, 4 out of 6; or 2 out of 2 indicating positive association); --? = results indicate preliminary support with 51-66% of reviews show negative association ($k \geq 3$, e.g., 2 out of 3, 4 out of 6; or 2 out of 2 yielding negative association); 00 = strong support of mixed or no associations for $\geq 51\%$ reviews ($k \geq 4$, e.g., 3 out of 4, 3 out of 5; or 3 out of 3 null/mixed association); 0 = results indicate preliminary support for null associations (for 2 out of 3 reviews, or 2 out of 2 reviews indicating null/mixed findings); ? = one review only, regardless of whether findings are mixed or significant and positive/negative.

Psychosocial determinants of alternative protein choices: a meta-review

Supplemental Material

Supplemental Material includes:

- **Full list of keywords used for systematic database search**
- **Additional information about search method:**
 - Grey Literature Searches
 - Coding Process
 - Data Analysis and Synthesis
- **Additional information about search results:**
 - Types of APF in included studies
 - Population
 - Types of Individual-Level Determinants
 - Design of Included Studies
- **Table S1** - *Description of Studies Included in the Meta-Review*
- **Table S2** - *Results of Coding of the Associations Between the Determinants (the COM-B Model Dimensions and Sociodemographic Characteristics) and Alternative Protein Food (APF) Choice Indicators Among Consumers*
- **Table S3** - *The Summary of the Risk of Bias Assessment in the Included Reviews (Evaluated Using the ROBIS Tool)*

Full list of keywords used for systematic database search

Determinants: AB (“accept*” OR “preference*” OR “willingness” OR buy OR “purchas*” OR “choice*” OR “behavio*” OR “perception*” OR “accessability” OR “availability” OR “affordab”* OR “belief*” OR “perceive*” OR “percep*” OR “cognit*” OR “motiv*” OR “ability” OR “skill*” OR “acceptab*” OR “intention*” OR “attitude*” OR “knowledge” OR “values” OR “literacy” OR “eat” OR “stigma” OR “consumption” OR “intake” OR “consumer choice” OR “habit*” OR “preference*” OR “vegetarian*” OR “flexitarian*” OR “lifestyle” OR “vegan*” OR “pescatarian” OR “pollotarian”)

Outcomes: AND AB (“cultured meat*” OR “in vitro meat*” OR “synthetic meat*” OR “seaweed*” OR “alga*” OR “insect*” OR “lupin*” OR “pulses” OR “legume*” OR “bean*” OR “dry pea” OR “chickpea*” OR “cow pea” OR “pigeon pea” OR “lentil*” OR “meat alternative*” OR “meat substitute*” OR “plant-based meat*” OR “meat analogue*” OR “rapeseed kernel protein*” OR “mealworm protein*” OR “krill protein*” OR “microbial protein*” OR “cultivated mushroom protein*” OR “fermented fungal protein*” OR “pea protein*” OR “meat analogue*” OR “hybrid meat” OR "non-meat protein sources" OR "novel plant-based alternatives" OR “plant-based proteins” OR “substitute meat protein” OR "insect-based food" OR "insect-based protein*" OR "larvae protein*" OR "cultured meat" OR "bacterial protein" OR "lab grown meat" OR "cultured meat-based proteins" OR "cultivated meat" OR "fusarium venenatum" OR "quorn" OR "texture vegetable protein*" OR “novel food*” OR “innovative food*” OR “alternative type* of food*”)

AND AB (“systematic review*” OR meta-synthesis OR meta-review OR “synthesis of data” OR "critical analysis of the literature" OR metaanaly* OR meta-analy* OR "meta analy*" OR "Retrospective analysis" OR "Qualitative analysis" OR "Quantitative analysis" OR "systematic map*" OR "systematic narrative" OR "systematic overview*" OR "systematic review*" OR "systematic assessment" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "bibliographic search" OR "database search" OR "search of database*" OR "electronic search" OR handsearch* OR "hand search*" OR "search by hand" OR "keyword search" OR "literature search" OR "search of literature" OR "search of the literature" OR "search term*" OR "systematic search" OR "comprehensive search" OR "manual search" OR "scoping study" OR "meta-study" OR "literature-based study" OR "studies were identified" OR "compilation of the literature" OR "compilation of studies" OR "inclusion criteria" OR "exclusion criteria" OR meta-regression OR "evidence map*" OR meta-evidence)

Additional Information About Method

Grey Literature Searches

The research team (HZ, AB, ZS, EK, MS, AS, FG, PC, TP, AK, BTN) conducted additional searches of the “grey literature” sources via Google Scholar tools. The results of these preliminary searches suggested that the reviews found in the “grey literature” (e.g., identified by Google searches but not published in any peer-review journals,) did not meet the criteria of systematic, realist, or scoping reviews. In particular, the reviews identified in the “grey literature” sources did not report methods of data search, and/or inclusion criteria, and/or approaches to data coding. Therefore, these reviews did not provide information allowing to evaluate the possibility of a systematic bias in reported results. Consequently, the research team decided not to conduct systematic searches of the “grey literature” sources.

Coding Process

The coding process involved categorizing the reviews on the following criteria:

- *Alternative protein food (APF)*, if the food products include proteins obtained from land plants, or sea plants such as algae, fungi, and insects, as these sources have been shown to have low environmental impact (Grossman & Weiss, 2021). Consistently with this definition, cultured meat was excluded because the technology is still in its early stages and its potential environmental benefits have been questioned (Grossman & Weiss, 2021). For the purpose of this review 4 broader groups of APF were distinguished, guided by results presented in included reviews: (i) plant-based APF, including microalgae-based APF; (ii) insect-based APF; (iii) mushroom/fungi-based APF; (iv) APF from various sources, including plant-, insect-, -fungi/mushroom-based proteins. The final category refers to cases where the results presented in the included reviews pertained to various alternative proteins, without specifying if the respective results are related, e.g., to plant-based APF only.
- The *APF choice indicators* included behavior indicators and its most proximal determinant, intention (Theory of Planned Behavior [Ajzen & Schmid, 2020] or Social Cognitive Theory [Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020]). Specifically, we included (1) intention to buy, intention to eat, and intention to pay; (2) self-reported behavior, including self-reported intake, or “adoption” defined as an incorporation of APF into own diet (Rogers, 2003); (3) the actual performance of a behavior (e.g., the number of times the product was actually purchased); (4) a broader category of “acceptance” of APF (cf. Onwezen et al. 2021), used in reviews summarizing purchase-related or intake-related behaviors and intentions, without specifying which is actually considered in a specific study.
- The *individual-level determinants*, included in the COM-B model (broad categories of capabilities, perceived opportunities, and motivations) or the sociodemographic individual-level characteristics, such as: age, gender, income, and education (cf. CICI

framework). When a determinant was named using a very broad term, e.g., an “attitude” and a specific definition or a reference to a definition was not provided, the findings were excluded due to the ambiguity of the construct. The examples are: “attitudes” or “persuasion drivers.” Other health behaviors, such as alcohol intake, exercise, but also vegetarian or vegan diet were excluded as the determinants, as behaviors or behavioral patterns are the outcomes of the determinants in the COM-B model. Actual environmental determinants (e.g., the ways the product is exposed in the supermarkets) or product-related determinants (e.g., its sensory characteristics, price) were excluded and are beyond the scope of this review.

Data Analysis and Synthesis

To analyze collected data we used a narrative synthesis method, based on the Economic and Social Research Council guidance (Campbell et al., 2019; Popay et al., 2006). First, a narrative synthesis uses a theoretical model to provide the underpinnings for the analyzed patterns of associations (Campbell et al., 2019; Popay et al., 2006). This review used the COM-B model and CICI framework (Pfadenhauer et al., 2019) as the theoretical underpinnings. Second, the preliminary synthesis should be provided, including an initial description of the results of included studies (e.g., their textual description, and characteristics of included reviews. In the present meta-review, we coded included studies along several categories (e.g., type of APF, the breadth of the determinants included) and provided a description of initial results. The third step of the narrative synthesis accounts for exploring the relationships in the data to identify patterns of associations and explain differences in association directions. Fourth, the narrative synthesis should account for an assessment of the robustness of the obtained results, for example using the quality assessment tools that address the respective risk of bias. This meta-review addressed the heterogeneity of included reviews in reference to the quality of included papers.

Additional Information About Results

Types of APF in Included Studies

Across the reviews, $k = 4$ specifically focused on plant-based APF (Baiano, 2020; Graça et al., 2019; He et al., 2020; Szenderák et al., 2022), $k = 13$ specifically addressed insect-based proteins (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021; Batat & Peter, 2020; Dagevos, 2020; Deroy et al., 2015; Florença et al., 2022, Kauppi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Mancini et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et al., 2021; Wendin & Nyberg, 2022; Wendt & Weinrich, 2023), whereas $k = 10$ investigated APF from various sources, including plant-based, insect-based, mushroom/fungi-based, and other APF (Eckl et al., 2021; Giordano et al., 2017; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Nguyen et al., 2022; Onwezen et al., 2021; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Weinrich, 2019). Only $k = 2$ addressed mushroom/fungi-based proteins (De Cianni et al., 2023; Eckl et al., 2021).

Population

The majority of included reviews synthesized data collected in Europe, North America, and Australia/New Zealand ($k = 21$, 75% out of 28). Seven reviews (25% out of 28) did not provide information regarding the countries of origin; however, the screening of included references suggests that these reviews provided data from developed countries (including European countries, North American countries, Australia, New Zealand, and Japan).

Types of Individual-Level Determinants

All reviews addressed a combination of various individual-level determinants, related to at least two areas of the COM-B model, whereas $k = 17$ reviews (Dagevos, 2020; De Cianni et al., 2023; Eckl et al., 2021; Florença et al., 2022; Graça et al., 2019; Kauppi et al., 2019; Kröger et al., 2022; Mancini et al., 2019; Mina et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022;

Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023; Szenderák et al., 2022; Toti et al., 2020; Wassmann et al., 2021; Weinrich, 2019; Wendin & Nyberg, 2022) directly analyzed the associations between APF and gender, age, income, or education. The vast majority of included reviews (26 out of 28) did not limit their scope to individual-level COM-B determinants and sociodemographic variables alone. Instead, they encompassed a broader range of determinants, including those related to the physical and social environment (i.e., product characteristics, sensory characteristics related to APF intake, production-related safety, physical environment characteristics, etc.).

Design of Included Studies

Across the reviews, only $k = 1$ reported results of a meta-analysis (Wassmann et al., 2021). Additionally, only four studies (Eckl et al., 2021; Hartmann & Siegriest, 2017; Kröger et al., 2022; Wendt & Weinrich, 2023) provided some descriptive statistics, clarifying a proportion of studies that indicated the associations between APF choice indicator and a respective individual-level determinant, compared with the total number of relevant original studies. The remaining $k = 23$ reviews provided a narrative synthesis of the associations, without any quantitative summary.

Table S1

Description of Studies Included in the Meta-Review

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
1	Ardoin & Prinyawitkul (2021)	5	13	USA, Italy, Switzerland	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	This review discusses current trends in perceptual entomophagy research in Australia, Canada, Europe and the USA since 2015, along with an analysis of the guiding theoretical approaches to predicting insect consumption.	not provided	not provided	review	2015-2020	This study was supported by the USDA NIFA Hatch project LAB94473, Louisiana State University Agricultural Center.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	9	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework work used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
2	Baiano (2022)	8	261	Switzerland, Australia, Canada	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN or more than 50% of countries (i.e., mainly these countries) + incl at least $n = 1$ EUR country	NO	a & b	This work is aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of 3D printed foods.	649	not provided	review	2010-2020	not provided	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	4	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)	
3	Batat & Peter (2020)	not provided	not provided	not provided	not provided	NO	not provided	The purpose of this paper introduces entomophagy as an alternative food consumption (AFC) capable of contributing to food well-being (FWB) among Western consumers. Specifically, it provides a conceptual framework where key factors related to the acceptance and adoption of insects and insect based foods are identified.	not provided	not provided	review	not provided	not provided	not provided	5	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
4	Dagevos (2021)	33	33	"Western countries"	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	not provided	This literature review presents established threads of research about: (1) Westerners' unfamiliarity with; and (2) fear of eating insects; or (3) consumer reactions to processed or unprocessed insect food products.	not provided	adults and young adults (Millennials and Generation Z), university students, vegan and vegetarians	review	2019	not provided	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	15	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

5	De Cianni et al. (2023)	27	31	Finland, Brazil, Portugal, Hungary, USA, India, Turkey, Malaysia, Nigeria, Brazil, Mexico, Sweden, Thailand	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	The main objectives are the identification and shaping of the key factors that determine consumption and purchasing behaviour toward edible mushrooms and mushroom products, providing an overview of key research issues and approaches and discussing the implications for industries and policymakers, as well as the identification of research gaps to be addressed in future studies. This article's aim is to suggest an alternative sensorially-driven strategy,	not provided	not provided	systematic review	2000-present	This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	10	no experimental studies	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details
6	Deroy et al. (2015)	not provided	not provided	not provided	not provided	NO	not provided		not provided	not provided	review	not provided	not provided	not provided	1	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/frame work used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
																which stands a much greater chance of making people eat insects on a regular basis.

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
7	Eckl et al. (2021)	23	23	UK, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Iceland, Romania, Italy, Netherlands, Hungary, Canada, USA, New Zealand, France, Belgium	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	The aim of this review is to identify the drivers and inhibitors underlying consumer behavior of replacing meat with non-meat protein sources in omnivores and flexitarians in developed countries.	10933	adults, meat consumers or flexitarians	narrative review	2011-2021	This work was supported by a research grant provided by the VLAG Graduate School of Wageningen University, Wageningen, The Netherlands. VLAG Graduate School had no role in this review including its conceptualization, design, execution, interpretation, and writing and revising of the manuscript.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	19	11 experimental studies	1 study on consumption of meat substitutes

8	Florença et al. (2022)	31	31	Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Brazil, Canada, Dominican Republic, Mexico, Peru, USA, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, China, India, Japan, Thailand, Australia, New Zealand	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	This work aims to: (1) examine the determinants positively and negatively influencing the consumption of insects; (2) see if the degree of acceptability differs between eating whole insects and insects incorporated in products; and finally, (3) if the determinants that influence the consumption diverge between insect-eating countries (IEC) and Western countries (WC).	20392	children, adolescents and adults	systematic review	2014-2021	This work was funded by CERNAS Research Centre (Polytechnic Institute of Viseu, Portugal) in the ambit of the project EISuFood (Ref. CERNAS-IPV/2020/003). We also received funding from the FCT—Foundation for Science and Technology (Portugal) through projects Ref. UIDB/00681/2020, UIDB/05507/2020, UIDB/007421/2020, UIDB/05748/2020, UIDP/05748/2020 and UIDB/00239/2020. The APC was funded by the FCT	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	17	no experimental studies	studies examined acceptance only
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No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
												through project Ref. UIDB/006 81/2020, project Ref. UIDB/055 07/2020 and project Ref. UIDB/007 421/2020.				

9	Giordano et al. (2018)	9	53	Germany, China, Belgium, USA, Netherlands, UK, Switzerland, Thailand	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	3482	consumers, habitual meat consumers, students, supermarket shoppers, not vegan or vegetarian, insect eaters and non-eaters	systematic review	2006-2016	not provided	7	1 experimental study	studies examined only cognitive factors
									This systematic review analyses and synthesizes the main results of recent studies dealing with food neophobia and neophilia with regard to new technologies applied to the food sector, both in the context of developed countries and in developing ones. In particular, main factors leading to caution and aversion for food technologies were identified and discussed, as well as different approaches to measure consumers' resistance to the mentioned technologies and to predict						This work was supported and funded by: (1) EU through Regione Puglia: "Avviso aiuti a sostegno dei Cluster Tecnologici Regionali per l'Innovazione" - Project: "PERFORM TECH (PUGLIA EMERGING FOOD TECHNOLOGY) - La sicurezza alimentare mediante l'impiego di tecnologie emergenti per l'elaborazione di prodotti funzionali, recupero di sostanze nutraceutiche dai sottoprodotti e valorizzazione energetica degli

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
							consumers' behavior.					scarti" - code LPIJ9P2; (2) AGER Foundation - OLIVE TREE and OIL: COMPETITIVE – Claims of Olive oil to iMProVE The market ValuE of the product.				

10	Graça et al. (2019)	66 (articles concerning plant-based diets and not meat reduction)	110	USA, UK, Croatia, Sweden, China, Greece, Australia, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Portugal, Canada, India, Finland, Italy, Hungary, Austria, Spain, Malaysia, Norway	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	YES - The COM-B Theoretical Model	a, b & c	The present review aims to address this limitation and has two specific objectives: (1) to map the variables (i.e., actual or potential barriers and enablers) known to be associated with meat curtailment, meat substitution and adherence to plant-based diets; (2) to integrate the current body of knowledge into a coherent overarching theoretical framework of behavior change (COM-B system).	241529	convenience sample, university students, meat eaters, meat reducers, vegetarians, university students, urban sample, general population, business students, adolescents, Mturk population, vegans, food shoppers, internet users, soldiers, ethnic minorities, students of environmental studies, medical students, food retail representatives, psychology students, flexitarians	systematic review	1989-2018	This work was supported by Programa Lisboa 2020, Portugal 2020 and the European Union through the European Regional Development Fund (LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-029348), by the state budget through the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (PTDC/PSI-GER/29348/2017), and by a grant from the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (SFRH/	not provided	22	21.3% of the studies were experiments or randomized controlled trial	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details
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No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
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11	Hartmann & Siegrist (2017)	38	USA, UK, Netherlands, Portugal, Australia (Victoria), Switzerland, Belgium, Germany, Turkish/Kurdish & Chinese/Hong Kongese migrants from Netherlands, France, China, Canada, Denmark, Italy	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	Research questions: 1) Are consumers aware that meat consumption has a large environmental impact? 2) Are consumers willing to reduce meat consumption or substitute meat with an alternative? 3) Are consumers willing to accept meat substitutes and alternative proteins, such as insects or cultured meat?	38947	convenience sample, students, visitors to an Insectarium, students interested in insect-food, Christian school students, university students, second-generation migrants in the Netherlands	systematic review	1997-2016	This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.	not provided	3	7 experimental studies	4 studies on actual consumption

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12	He et al. (2020)	not provided	not provided	not provided	not provided	NO	a & b	The aim of this review was to gather current knowledge on plant-based meat alternatives	not provided	not provided	review	not provided	Education department of Hunan province China, Grant/Award Number: 18B399; China Scholarship Council (CSC), Grant/Award Number: CSC 201908430017; Agriculture Food Canada, Grant/Award Number: J-000991	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	4	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

13	Kauppi et al. (2019)	not provided	not provided	"Western countries"	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	<p>This literature review focuses on the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the justifications for insect-eating presented in current literature and how do they reflect consumers' concerns? • What factors are understood as influencing consumer acceptance of insects as food? • How can design interventions address these factors and support the adoption of edible insects? 	not provided	not provided	review	2005-2018	<p>This article is a result of the ENTOWASTE project 'Design of insect and insect-based food products', funded by the Norwegian Research Council NFR (project number 271053/E50) under the ERANET LAC II scheme, a Network of the European Union (EU), Latin America and the Caribbean Countries (LAC) on Join Innovation and Research Activities.</p>	not provided	9	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details
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14	Kröger et al. (2021)	119	119	Czech Republic, USA, Italy, Belgium, Poland, Canada, Switzerland, Germany, Hungary, UK, Spain, Australia, Denmark, Netherlands, Finland, France, Sweden, New Zealand	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	This systematic review sought to identify, analyze, and synthesize the findings of empirical studies on consumer acceptance of insect-based food products in Western countries.	53493	adults, young adults, university students, undergraduate students, school children, both from urban and rural areas	systematic review	2013-2021	We acknowledge support by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) and Open Access Publishing Fund of Osnabrück University	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	23	34 experimental studies	3 studies on actual consumption as dependent variable

15	Onwezen et al. (2021)	91	91	The majority of the studies were conducted in the Netherlands (20 studies), Italy (17 studies), Germany (13 studies), the United States (9 studies), Australia (8 studies), Belgium (7 studies), the United Kingdom (5 studies), and Switzerland (6 studies). Other countries, such as the Czech Republic, are only represented once or twice.	D) - EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	Overview of drivers of acceptance of a wide range of alternative proteins.	51333	the particular age range, gender or socio-economic status was not specified	systematic review	2005-2020	The review is conducted in a research project on alternative proteins funded by the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality.	not provided	24	40 experimental studies	8 studies on actual consumption
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16	Mancini et al. (2019)	41	41	Czech Republic, Italy, Belgium, Poland, Netherlands, Hungary, Switzerland, Germany, China, Denmark, France, Australia, Sweden, Ireland, Thailand	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	This review article analyzed different methodologies conducted on European consumers and categorized the studies in relation to the type of analysis chosen, data collection and results obtained.	12930	students with part-time occupation plus employees in several jobs, undergraduate students, students, university students and employees, consumers from outside the university, staff and students of AgroParisTech, participants at a “bug banquet”, university students of Gastronomy and Food Science courses of the Department of Food Science, adults with various education level	review	2012-2019	This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	6	8 experimental studies	9 studies examined actual consumption via tasting

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
17	Mina et al. (2023)	62	Italy, Germany, Netherlands, Belgium, Poland, UK, Switzerland, Finland, France, Romania, Portugal, Sweden, Hungary, Ireland, Denmark, Spain, Norway, Czech Republic	B) Europe only	NO	a & b	Research Question 1 (RQ1): Among the variables analyzed in the literature, which appear to be barriers and which drivers for the consumption of insects in Europe? Research Question 2 (RQ2): Considering what emerged from the first research question, which are the most promising strategies to convince European consumers to eat insects?	not provided	general consumers, university students, minors, millennials, gen z, older people, consumers who have already eaten insects, participants in a health fair, university staff	systematic review	2015-2022	This research received no external funding.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	11	5 experimental studies	6 studies examined previous consumption

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18	Nguyen et al. (2022)	64	64	Netherlands, United States, Finland, Sweden, Germany, Czech Republic, Belgium, France, Switzerland, Australia, New Zealand, Denmark, United Kingdom, Canada, Italy, Brazil, Spain, Dominican Republic, Scotland, Poland, Portugal, South Korea, China	D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	YES - The COM-B Theoretical Model	a & b	To review existing literature and identify key factors influencing alternative proteins consumption; to extrapolate the relevance of these factors to the marketing domain.	48443	both men and women, age range - 15-100; children, students, adults and older adults	systematic review	2004-2021	The research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.	not provided	23	13 experimental articles	17 studies examined actual consumption and consumption decision making

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19	Siddiqui, Bahmid et al. (2023)	76	UK, Portugal, The Netherlands, Italy, Belgium, Switzerland, Germany, China, Denmark, USA, France, Spain, Romania, New Zealand, Australia, Finland, Sweden, Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	This paper focuses on in-depth understanding of consumer perception and acceptability of plant-, seaweed-, and insect-based meat products to get insights on their current situation and future implementation.	50664	adult consumers	review	2012-2021	The author(s) reported there is no funding associated with the work featured in this article.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	17	3 experimental studies	2 studies examined actual consumption

20	Siddiqui, Zannou, et al. (2022)	133	133	Europe, Asia, North America	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	This paper reviews articles to arrange appropriate strategies for reducing neophobia and increasing consumer acceptance of novel foods and new food technologies.	not provided	children, young adults & adults; urban and rural	review	2012-2021	This study was supported by the research project entitled “Sustainable up-cycling of agricultural residues: modular cascading waste conversion system” (research grant agreement No. FACCE SURPLUS /III/UpWaste/02/2020) funded by the National (Polish) Center for Research and Development (NCBiR) (FACCE SURPLUS /III/UpWaste/02/2020 project). Research is partially funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	6	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details
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No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
21	Siddiqui, Alvi, et al. (2022)	28	33	Finland, Belgium, Canada, Germany, China, USA, UK, Italy, Japan, Switzerland, India, Columbia, Denmark, Australia, Chile, Sweden, The Netherlands	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	11337	adults, children, adolescents	systematic review	2016-2022	Research (BMBF), in the frame of FACCE-SURPLUS /FACCE-JPI project UpWaste, grant number 031B0934 A. The review is partly conducted in a funded project by the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (KB37-Healthy and safe food systems).	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	16	4 experimental studies	no studies on actual consumption

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
22	Szenderák et al. (2022)	28	28	India, Europe, USA, China, Korea, Germany, Japan, Belgium, Canada, South Africa, Turkey	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a & b	In this review, the factors affecting the consumer acceptance of plant-based meat substitutes were analyzed and systematically summarized	37332	not provided	narrative review	2016-2022	This research received no external funding.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	22	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
23	Toti et al. (2020)	19	19	Italy, Denmark	B) Europe only	NO	a & b	The purpose of this narrative paper is to provide an overview of the main topics related to entomophagy.	39179	international university students, Italian university students, employees and consumers from outside the university, university students with part-time occupation, employees in several jobs, individuals recruited in a "bug banquet", university staff, just graduates	narrative review	not provided	This research received no external funding.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	15	2 experimental studies	5 studies that examined actual consumption via tasting sessions

24	Wang et al. (2023)	not provided	not provided	not provided	not provided	NO	not provided	This review summarizes the potential applications of algae-derived bioactive compounds, as well as their application status to improve the quality of meat and meat products.	not provided	not provided	review	not provided	Min Wang and Jianjun Zhou were supported by a PhD fellowship from the China Scholarship Council (CSC) (No. 201908420245 and No. 201908420246, respectively). Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro and FCT/MCT for the financial support for the LAQV research unit (UIDB/50006/2020) through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	3	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details
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No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
												and to the Portuguese NMR Network, and for financing the PhD grant of Jéssica Tavares and Carlos A. Pinto (2021.07264.BD and SFRH/BD/137036/2018, respectively).				

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
25	Wassmann et al. (2021)	37	USA, Switzerland, Thailand, Netherlands, Germany, Finland, Hungary, China, Denmark, Italy, Belgium, UK, India	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	Our findings aim to consolidate the existing body of knowledge on the barriers to and potential avenues for the acceptance of edible insects and may also illuminate the next steps appropriate for entomophagy acceptance research.	18255	not provided	meta-analysis	2012-2020	not provided	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	17	8 experimental studies	review researched only willingness to consume
26	Weinrich (2019)	27	UK, Belgium, South Africa, Italy, The Netherlands, Malaysia, Taiwan, USA, Canada	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	YES - innovation-decision process	a & b	The aim of this paper is to review consumer research dealing with consumers' adoption of meat substitutes.	16514	consumers, students, meat-eaters, users of meat substitutes, vegetarians, general population	review	1975-2017	The publication was funded by the Lower Saxony Vorab by the Ministry of Science and Culture (MWK).	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	3 experimental studies	6 studies that examined actual consumption via tasting sessions and 1 study that examined experience with previous consumption	

No.	Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
27	Wendin & Nyberg (2021)	not provided	not provided	not provided	not provided	NO	not provided	The main objective of this review was to identify the key factors influencing consumer perception and acceptability of insect-based foods described in the literature published in recent years.	not provided	not provided	review	2019-2020	Funded by the research environment MEAL (Food and Meals in Everyday Life), Kristianstad University, Sweden.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	23	not discussed in detail	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

No. Reference	Number of original studies on psychosocial determinants of AP intake	Number of original studies	Region/country where the original studies were conducted	Regions*	Was any theory/framework used to guide/organize the findings of the systematic review?	Design of original studies: a) quantitative b) qualitative c) mixed methods	Objectives of the systematic review	N of participants	Population	Type of review (systematic review, scoping review, narrative review etc.)	Time span of original studies	Funding	Conflict of interest	How many times data from the respective review were included in analyses conducted in this meta-review?	Design of original studies (number of experimental studies as reported in the results of the included review)	Dependent variable: Actual intake/consumption (as reported in the results section of the original review included in this meta-review)
28	Wendt & Weinrich (2023)	49	49	Australia, Canada, Italy, South Korea, Belgium, Poland, Brazil, Finland, Chile, Uganda, Switzerland, Mexico, China, Germany, USA, Netherlands, Spain, Dominican Republic	C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN & D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN	NO	a	24557	1) Is the FTNS a suitable tool to measure consumer acceptance of novel food technologies? 2) What is the impact of FTN on willingness to try products created using novel technologies? 3) What research areas should be addressed in future studies?	in most studies (except one) participants were from well-developed countries, majority of the studies (43) had non-representative sample	2008-2022	This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.	All authors declared no conflicts of interest.	1	no experimental studies	operationalization of dependent variable not discussed in details

Note. *-Regions were grouped: A) USA, Canada, AUS/NZ only or more than 50% of countries (i.e., mainly these countries) WITHOUT ANY EUR country; B) Europe only; C) Countries apart from EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN; D) EUR, AUS/NZ, USA, CAN or more than 50% of countries (i.e., mainly these countries) + incl at least n = 1 EUR country; E) USA only or Canada only; AP – alternative proteins; AUS/NS – Australia/New Zealand; CAN – Canada; EUR – Europe; USA – United States of America.

Table S2

Results of Coding of the Associations Between the Determinants (the COM-B Model Dimensions and Sociodemographic Characteristics) and Alternative Protein Food (APF) Choice Indicators Among Consumers

COM-B model and sociodemographic individual-level determinants of APF choice	APF choice indicators	Plant-based APF: reviews providing evidence for the association	Insect-based APF: reviews providing evidence for the association	Food made with any alternative proteins (e.g., based on sources from plants, insects, mycoproteins, etc.): reviews providing evidence for the association	
COM-B: CAPABILITIES					
Perceived cooking skills (referring to preparing meals with respective alternative protein components)	Intention to eat			+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)	
	Acceptability	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)			
	Self-reported intake or adoption of a diet	+ (Eckl et al., 2021) + (Graça et al., 2019) + (He et al., 2020)		+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)	
Purchase activism (a trait describing customers' motivation to express opinions and influence the marketplace via purchases)	Intention to buy		+ (Kröger et al., 2022)		
Mindfulness	Acceptability		0 (Dagevos, 2020) 0 (Kröger et al., 2022)		
Easiness to replace meat with APF (perceived convenience)	Intention to buy			+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)	
	Acceptability		+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)	
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		0 (Wassmann, et. al., 2021)		
	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	+ (Florença et al., 2022)		
Formal knowledge about the positive effects of food consumption and the respective types of food	Intention to eat		+ (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021) + (Kauppi et al., 2019) + (Mancini et al., 2019) + (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022)		
		Intention to buy	+ (Eckl et al., 2021)	+ (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021)	
		Intention to pay	+ (Eckl et al., 2021)	+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022)	
	Acceptability of food		0 (Baiano, 2020) 0 (Eckl et al., 2021)	+ (Batat & Peter, 2020) + (Mina et al., 2023) + (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) + (Weinrich, 2019) 0 (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023) 0 (novel food; Giordano et al., 2017)
				+ (Eckl et al., 2021)	
		Adoption of a diet		+ (Florença et al., 2022)	
Perceived process of getting more information	Self-reported adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)			

Information provided to those interested in nutritional or ecological benefits of eating behavior (information provided to susceptible people)	Intention to eat		+ (Dagevos, 2020)		
	Intention to eat		+ (Kauppi et al., 2019)		
	Intention to buy	+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)	+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)		
	Acceptability of food			+ (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021)	
				+ (Dagevos, 2020)	
				+ (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023)
				+ (Kröger et al., 2022)	+ (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017)
				+ (Mancini et al., 2019)	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
				+ (Mina et al., 2023)	+ (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
				+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	
+ (Toti et al., 2020)					
Perceived familiarity/multiple exposures to APF	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)		
			+ (Wassmann et al. 2021)		
				- (meta-analysis - Wassmann et al. 2021)	
				+ (for past experience; meta-analysis - Wassmann et al. 2021)	
				0 (for mere familiarity; meta-analysis - Wassmann et al. 2021)	
	Self-reported intake/adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)			
	Reduced neophobia		+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)		
	Adoption of a diet		+ (Florença et al., 2022)	+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)	
	Early adopters (intention to try, but not necessarily maintain)		+ (Dagevos, 2020)		
COM-B: OPPORTUNITIES					
Positive social norms (food accepted by peers, family or experts)	Intention to try		+ (Mina et al., 2023)		
			+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)		
	Intention to eat			+ (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021)	
				+ (Kauppi et al., 2019)	
	Acceptability of specific types of food			+ (Kröger et al., 2022)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023)
+ (Mancini et al., 2019)				+ (mushroom-based product; Eckl et al., 2021)	
+ (Mina et al., 2023)				+ (Giordano et al., 2017)	
			+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)	
				+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)	
			+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)		

	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		+ (Wassmann, et al., 2021)	
	Adoption of a diet		+ (Florença et al., 2022)	
Positive social norm regarding eating meat	Acceptability of intake	– (He et al., 2020)		– (Nguyen et al., 2022)
Social support from family and friends to follow a meatless diet	Self-reported intake	+ (Graça et al., 2019)		
Social identity (sociability and positive social image of non-eating meat)	Intention to eat			+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)
	Intention to eat		+ (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Intention to eat		+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022)	
			+ (Batai & Peter, 2020)	
			+ (novel insect-based food; Giordano et al., 2017)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023)
Positive cultural norms	Acceptability of food		+ (Kauppi et al., 2019)	+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)
			+ (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017)	+ (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
			+ (Mancini et al., 2019)	
			+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	
			+ (Toti et al., 2020)	
			+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	Self-reported intake		+ (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Adoption of a diet		+ (Florença et al., 2022)	
Incompatibility with local food	Adoption			– (Weinrich, 2019)
Perceived as unsafe	Acceptability of food	– (Baiano, 2020)	– (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	– (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
Perceived as safe	Intention to eat		+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	Intention to buy		+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	Intention to purchase	– (Szenderák et al., 2022)		– (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
	Acceptability	– (Onwezen et al., 2021)	– (Kröger et al., 2022)	– (Eckl et al., 2021)
Perceived artificialness, technology distrust/food technology neophobia				– (Giordano et al., 2017)
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		– (Wassmann et al., 2021)	
	Adoption of a diet		– (Florença et al., 2022)	
			– (Wendt & Weinrich, 2023)	
Low perceived uncertainty/high trust (in research, science, independent promoters/organizations)	Acceptability	+ (algae-based only; Onwezen et al., 2021)	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	+ (novel food; Giordano et al., 2017)
				+ (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
COM-B: MOTIVATIONS				
	Intention to eat		+ (Toti et al., 2020)	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
	Intention to buy	+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)		+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
Health benefits, perceived healthiness		+ (Graça et al., 2019)	+ (Dagevos, 2020)	
	Acceptability of food	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	0 (Kröger et al., 2022)	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)
		+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)
		+ (algae-based only; Wang et al., 2023)	+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)

	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		0 (Wassmann et al., 2021)	
	Self-reported intake	+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022)		+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023)
	Adoption	+ (Eckl et al., 2021) + (Weinrich, 2019)	+ (Florença et al., 2022)	
Positive expected outcomes (well-being related)	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)		
High nutritional value	Intention to eat		– (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	Acceptability of food	+ (algae-based only; Wang et al., 2023)	0 (Wang et al., 2023) + (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	A perceived barrier for intake		– (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022)	
Perceived health risks	Acceptability		– (Batat & Peter, 2020) – (Onwezen et al., 2021)	
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		– (Wassmann, et. Al., 2021)	+ (Giordano et al., 2017)
	Adoption of a diet	– (He et al., 2020)	– (Florença et al., 2022)	
Perceived unhealthiness	Acceptability of food	– (Baiano, 2020)		
Beliefs about meat healthiness	Intention to eat			– (Nguyen et al., 2022)
	Intention to eat	+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)	0 (Kröger et al., 2022) 0 (Mina et al., 2023) + (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) 0 (Weinrich, 2019) 0 (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023) 0 (Nguyen et al., 2022) + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
	Intention to buy	0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)	+ (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	+ (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023) + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
	Intention to pay		0 (Kröger et al., 2022) 0 (Dagevos, 2020) 0 (Kröger et al., 2022) + (Mancini et al., 2019) 0 (Mina et al., 2023) + (Onwezen et al., 2021) + (Toti et al., 2020) 0 (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
Perceived pro-environmental beliefs and sustainability motives	Acceptability of food	+ Onwezen et al., 2021		
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		+ (Wassmann, et. Al., 2021)	
	Higher intake	+ (Eckl et al., 2021) + (Graça et al., 2019)	+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) + (Toti et al., 2020)	+ (Eckl et al., 2021) 0 (Nguyen et al., 2022) + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)
	Actual purchase	0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)		
	Adoption, regular purchase		+ (Florença et al., 2022)	+ (Weinrich, 2019)

Climate change skepticism	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	– (Graça et al., 2019)	
Concerns about animal suffering/empathy towards animals	Intention to eat	+ (Eckl et al., 2021); + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)	
	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	+ (Florença et al., 2022)
Moral or ethical motives	Acceptance	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021)	
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		+ (Wassmann, et. Al., 2021)
Moral disengagement	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	– (Graça et al., 2019)	
Following conservative values/conseervative views	Acceptability		– (Onwezen et al., 2021)
	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	0 (Graça et al., 2019) 0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)	
Religion	Acceptability		0 (Kröger et al., 2022) + (Kauppi et al., 2019) + (sustainability; Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) + (younger men; Wendin & Nyberg, 2021) + (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021) + (Kröger et al., 2022) + (Wassmann et al., 2021) + (Florença et al., 2022) + (Dagevos, 2020) + (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021) + (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021) + (Dagevos, 2020) + (Onwezen et al., 2021) + (Toti et al., 2020) + (Florença et al., 2022) + (Kröger et al., 2022) + (Dagevos, 2020) – (Szenderák et al., 2022) 0 (Szenderák et al., 2022) – (Graça et al., 2019) – (Szenderák et al., 2022) – (plant-based meat alternatives; He et al., 2020) 0 (Kröger et al., 2022)
Being daring, adventurous, sensation seeking, extreme emotions	Intention to eat		
	Acceptance		
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		
	Adoption of a diet		
	Early adopters, ready to try (but not necessary to maintain)		
Curiosity	Intention to try		
	Acceptability		
	Adoption of a diet		
Food neophilia	Acceptance		
Meat attachment and positive emotions while eating meat	Intention to eat		
	Purchase likelihood		
	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet		
	Adoption		

Worry and guilt towards eating meat	Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)		+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)
Neophobia	Intention to try/eat		— (Nguyen et al., 2022) – (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) – (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Intention to pay		– (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Acceptance	– (only algae based-food and plant-based meat alternatives; Onwezen et al., 2021)	– (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021) – (Batat & Peter, 2020) – (Dagevos, 2020) – (Kröger et al., 2022) – (Mina et al., 2023) – (Nguyen et al., 2022) – (Onwezen et al., 2021) – (Toti et al., 2020) – (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	– (various meat replacement alternatives; Eckl et al., 2021) – (Siddiqui, Zannou et al., 2022)
	Intake self-reported	– (Graça et al., 2019) 0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)	– (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) – (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		– (meta-analysis – Wassmann et al., 2021)	
	Adoption of a diet		– (Florença et al., 2022)	
	Early adopters (willing to try, but not necessarily to maintain)		– (Dagevos, 2020)	
	Intention to try		– (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) – (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021) – (Batat & Peter, 2020) – (Deroy et al., 2015)	
	Acceptance	– (only algae based-food and plant-based meat alternatives; Onwezen et al., 2021)	– (tendency to react with disgust on various stimuli; Kröger et al., 2022) – (Mina et al., 2023) – (Onwezen et al., 2021) – (Toti et al., 2020) – (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
	Various indicators (intention to consume, try, pay for)		– (meta-analysis – Wassmann et al., 2021)	
Self-efficacy for dietary change	Adoption of a diet		– (Florença et al., 2022)	
	Intention to eat/ intention to buy		+ (Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul, 2021)	
	Acceptability Self-reported intake/ adoption of a diet	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	+ (Kröger et al., 2022)	+ (Onwezen et al., 2021) + (Giordano et al., 2017)
Openness to novelty	Intention to try			+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)
	Initial adoption of a diet (but not maintenance)			+ (Nguyen et al., 2022)

Extraversion, openness	Intention to pay, intention to eat		+ (Kröger et al., 2022)	
Agreeableness, neuroticism	Intention to pay, intention to eat		0 (Kröger et al., 2022)	
CICI CONEXT: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DETERMINANTS				
	Intention to eat	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	– (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) 0 (Toti et al., 2020)	
	Intention to buy	0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)		
	Intention to pay	0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)		
	Acceptability	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	– (Dagevos, 2020) – (Kauppi et al., 2019) – (Kröger et al., 2022) – (Mina et al., 2023) 0 (Mancini et al., 2019) – (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023) – (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	
Gender: women	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		– (Wassmann, et. al., 2021)	
	Intake	+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023)		0 (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023) 0 (mushroom-based products Eckl et al., 2021)
	Early adopters (willing to try, but not necessarily to maintain)		– (Dagevos, 2020)	
	Adoption of a diet	0 (Nguyen et al., 2022)	– (Florença et al., 2022) 0 (Nguyen et al., 2022) – (Weinrich, 2019)	
	Self-reported intake	– (Szenderák et al., 2022)		
Gender/age as moderator	Acceptability	+ (older women; Szenderák et al., 2022)	– (no gender differences for unprocessed APF, gender differences in case of processed APF; Kröger et al., 2022)	
	Trying (initial adoption)		+ (younger men; Kauppi et al., 2019)	
Gender as a moderator	Health, production type and nutrition motivation (important among women but not men)			+ (Eckl et al., 2021)
Age/gender as a moderator of the effectiveness of education interventions	Intention to adopt a diet	+ (younger women; Nguyen et al., 2022)	+ (younger men; Kauppi et al., 2019)	
	Intention to eat	0 Nguyen, 2022		
Age: younger consumers	Acceptability	0 (Graça et al., 2019)	0 (Kröger et al., 2022) + (Mina et al., 2023)	+ (mushroom-based products; Eckl et al., 2021)

		+ (Toti et al., 2020) + (Weinrich, 2019) + (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021)	0 (Nguyen et al., 2022)
	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)	0 (meta-analysis - Wassmann, et al., 2021)	
	Trying (not maintenance)	+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)	- (in children; Kröger et al., 2022)
	Intake	+ (Siddiqui, Alvi et al., 2022) + (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023) + (Szenderák et al., 2022)	0 (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023)
	Early adopters (willing to try, but not necessary maintain)		+ (Dagevos, 2020)
	Intention to adopt		+ (Eckl et al., 2021)
	Adoption of a diet		+ (Florença et al., 2022)
	Acceptability	+ (Graça et al., 2019); + (higher plant intake; Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023) (higher plant intake); + (Szenderák et al., 2022)	0 (Eckl et al., 2021); 0 (Kauppi et al., 2019); 0 (Kröger et al., 2022); + (Mina et al., 2023); + (Wendin & Nyberg, 2021) 0 (mushroom-based products; De Cianni et al., 2023) 0 (mushroom-based products; Eckl et al., 2021) 0 (Nguyen et al., 2022)
Higher education status	Various indicators (intention to: consume, try, pay for)		0 (meta-analysis -Wassmann, et al., 2021 – meta- analysis)
	Early adopters (willing to try, but not necessarily maintain)		+ (Dagevos, 2020)
	Intake	+ (Szenderák et al., 2022)	
	Intention to pay	0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)	
	Acceptability	+ (Graça et al., 2019)	0 (mushroom-based products; Eckl et al., 2021)
Higher income status	Intake	+ (Siddiqui, Bahmid et al., 2023); 0 (Szenderák et al., 2022)	
	Adoption		+ (Florença et al., 2022)

Note: 0 – the review is providing either (1) mixed evidence, e.g., indicating that some original studies yielded significant positive associations while others yielded no associations; (2) non-significant evidence, that is included original research suggested no significant evidence ; - the review is providing evidence for the negative association, i.e., there is a significant negative link between the individual-level determinant and the indicator of APF choices; +- the review is providing evidence for the positive association, i.e., there is a significant positive link between the individual-level determinant and the indicator of APF choices. APF – alternative protein food; mushroom-based products - the reviews addressing mushroom and fungi-based alternative proteins only.

Table S3

The Summary of the Risk of Bias Assessment in the Included Reviews (Evaluated Using the ROBIS Tool)

No.	Included review	PHASE 2				PHASE 3
		1. Study eligibility criteria	2. Identification and selection of studies	3. Data collection and study appraisal	4. Synthesis and findings	Risk of bias in the review
1	Ardoin & Prinyawiwatkul (2021)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
2	Baiano (2022)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
3	Batat & Peter (2020)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
4	Dagevos (2021)	LOW	LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH
5	De Cianni et al. (2023)	LOW	LOW	HIGH	LOW	LOW
6	Deroy et al. (2015)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
7	Eckl et al. (2021)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
8	Florença et al. (2022)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
9	Giordano et al. (2018)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
10	Graça et al. (2019)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
11	Hartmann & Siegrist (2017)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
12	He et al. (2020)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
13	Kauppi et al. (2019)	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
14	Kröger et al. (2021)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
15	Mancini et al. (2019)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
16	Mina et al. (2023)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
17	Nguyen et al. (2022)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
18	Onwezen et al. (2021)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
19	Siddiqui, Bahmid et al. (2023)	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW
20	Siddiqui, Zannou, et al. (2022)	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	HIGH
21	Siddiqui, Alvi, et al. (2022)	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	HIGH
22	Szenderák et al. (2022)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

23	Toti et al. (2020)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
24	Wang et al. (2023)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
25	Wassmann et al. (2021)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
26	Weinrich (2019)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
27	Wendin & Nyberg (2021)	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
28	Wendt & Weinrich (2023)	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

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